

NANO-RUBBER TOUGHENING IN EPOXY AND EPOXY/CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES: TEMPERATURE EFFECT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present our recent work on the nano-rubber toughening effects on bulk epoxy and epoxy/carbon fibre composites tested in the temperature range -80°C to 50°C. The rubber toughening mechanisms and toughening efficiencies in both materials have been discussed. It is demonstrated that addition of nano-rubber particles can toughen both bulk epoxy and epoxy/carbon fibre laminates at all test temperatures; however, the toughness increase depends on the testing temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION---RUBBER TOUGHENING IN EPOXY AND EPOXY/FIBRE COMPOSITES

Amongst all the applications of fibre reinforced composites, laminated composites are the most common. Since the fibres can only provide in-plane reinforcement to the composite, the resistance to interlaminar crack growth, i.e., delamination, of the composite mainly relies on the fracture toughness of the matrix material. Epoxies are widely used as matrices for fibre reinforced composites. The highly cross-linked structure of epoxy yields many useful properties, such as high elastic modulus, high failure strength and high creep resistance. However, most epoxies are brittle. Delamination has been a major failure in their composites and this drawback has limited their wider applications. Substantial endeavours have been constantly made by researchers to develop new and innovative techniques to protect composites from delamination. An effective approach to increase the toughness of composite structures against delamination is to toughen the matrix material by adding micro-sized or nano-sized fillers.

Compared to other fillers, rubber particles have shown the highest ability in toughening the epoxy due to their capability of cavitation leading to large matrix shear deformation [1]. However, even if the resin shows excellent properties in bulk form, it may not be useful in laminated composites. To study the toughening effect of liquid rubber (LR) and core-shell rubber (CSR) in composite laminates, experimental studies were conducted on double-cantilever-beams (DCB) under mode-I loading by Yan et al. [2]. Three different materials were used as the matrices and they are: pure epoxy (DGEBA); 15% LR (CTBN) modified epoxy; and 15% CSR modified epoxies. The critical *J*-integral values of the composite laminates were compared to those of the bulk matrix materials in Figure 1, wherein the 1:1

straight line via the origin is superposed to indicate a full toughness transfer from the bulk matrices to the fibre laminates. Obviously, the toughening effect of either LR or CSR to neat epoxy is significant. Especially, with 15% CSR, the modified epoxy toughness is ~18 times the neat epoxy toughness. But when these rubber toughened epoxies are used as matrices of the laminates, their enhanced toughness cannot be completely transferred to the interlaminar fracture toughness of the carbon fibre reinforced laminates. As shown in Figure 1, J -integral values of laminates with toughened matrices are increased by 139% (LR) and 50% (CSR) compared to the non-toughened laminates. As explained in [2], the stiff carbon fibres have constrained the deformation capacities of the rubber modified epoxy matrices, thus reducing their full toughening effect. The loss of matrix toughness is more substantial in CSR than LR.

Figure 1 J-integral of carbon fibre composites *versus* J-integral of bulk matrix materials [2].

It has been proven that epoxy with smaller size fillers has higher toughness than that with larger size fillers [3-5]. In recent years, we have conducted a systematic study on toughening of bulk epoxy using nano-sized rubber particles [6]. The fracture energy, G_{IC} , of these nano-rubber modified epoxies increases with increasing particle loading. More importantly, due to the small size of the nano-rubber particles, they overcome the disadvantages of micro-rubber [2] and transfer more toughness from the modified epoxy matrix to the composite laminates. In our recent work [7], the delamination behaviour of carbon fibre/epoxy laminates was studied by DCB mode I delamination tests. The epoxy matrix was modified by adding nano-rubber particles and an increase in the interlaminar fracture toughness was obtained. The results in [6-7] are shown in Figure 2. There are two important points. First, compared to composite laminates with neat epoxy matrix, G_{IC} of nano-rubber modified composite laminates are all increased (from 40% at 4 wt% to 155% at 10 wt% particles). Hence, the toughening efficiency is higher than micro-rubber (CSR or LR, Figure 1) particles which require 15 wt% for similar toughness improvements. Second, the transferability of the matrix toughness at ≤ 6 wt% nano-rubber is more than 100% (owing to the occurrence of crack-wake bridging). At ≥ 8 wt% nano-rubber, the matrix toughness transferability is reduced and becomes worst at 12 wt%. Nonetheless, these reductions are much less than the micro-rubber (CSR or LR, Figure 1). These results therefore suggest nano-rubber is superior to micro-rubber in delamination toughening.

The above-mentioned results of nano-rubber modified epoxies and their fibre composites were all measured at room temperature. They cannot be used for design in some real engineering applications, such as in extreme environmental conditions where the temperature changes from sub-zero to elevated values. Low and Mai [20] examined the Charpy impact fracture energies and failure mechanisms of

micro-rubber modified epoxies over a range of temperatures. Their results indicated that micro-rubber particles increased G_{IC} of epoxy at -40 and 60 °C but reduced G_{IC} at room temperature. Cardwell and Yee [10] studied the temperature effects from -15 to 40 °C on fracture toughness, K_{IC} , of epoxy with 0.30 µm diameter rubber particles with loading speed from 0.01 in/min to 1.0 in/min. Their K_{IC} results obeyed the time-temperature superposition principle giving a master curve at 25 °C. Generally, K_{IC} of rubber modified epoxy increased with temperature but decreased with strain rate. Although these investigations have unveiled the significant effects of temperature on micro-rubber toughening, there is little published information on nano-rubber toughening of neat epoxy and its fibre laminates. To redress this problem, fracture toughness/fracture energy and toughening mechanisms of nano-rubber modified epoxies and their composite laminates will be studied under testing temperatures from -80 °C to 50 °C.

Figure 2 Delamination toughness of nano-rubber modified epoxy and their fibre laminates.

3 NANO-RUBBER TOUGHENING AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURE

3.1 Sample preparation

The bulk specimens for fracture toughness measurements were based on an epoxy resin, Araldite-F (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, DGEBA), and hardener, piperidine, both supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. The spherical rubber particles averaged ~100 nm in diameter and 25 wt% loading in bisphenol A resin was supplied in master batch by Kaneka Corporation, Japan. Neat epoxy resin and 6 wt% nano-rubber modified epoxy resin (by diluting the master batch with added epoxy) were prepared. The composite laminates for mode I interlaminar fracture toughness were fabricated from plain woven carbon fibres (168058ITL supplied by Inter-Turbine Advanced Logistics Pty Ltd, Australia) with a planar density of 203g/m³.

Neat epoxy and rubber-modified epoxy were heated to 60 °C and mixed continuously by magnetic stirring until a clear mixture was obtained, which was then degassed at 100 °C by evacuating for 1 h to ensure no bubble was trapped in the solution. Subsequently, a stoichiometric curing agent with a ratio of 100:5 was added and gently stirred. The final mixture was poured into a preheated mould for curing at 120 °C for 16 h. Following ASTM D5045-99 [11] single edge-notched beams (SENB) measuring 62 (length) x 12.5 (width) x 6.2 (thickness) mm³ were used for fracture toughness tests. A natural crack was introduced to each SENB specimen by tapping with a sharp razor blade. The composite laminates were fabricated by 16-ply of ~750 cm² woven carbon fibre fabric using a lay-up method and a 200 µm thick Kapton[®] polyimide film was inserted between the 8th and 9th plies to serve as initial cracks. The laminates were wrapped with bleeders and release film within a vacuum bag, and first vacuumed in a

chamber for 0.33 h followed by curing in a hot-press at 120 °C for 16 h. A pressure of 250 kPa was applied during curing to maintain a uniform laminate thickness (3.1 mm) and a constant fibre volume fraction ($60 \pm 2\%$). DCB specimens (125 mm in length x 20 mm in width) were finally cut from the square panels by a wet-jet diamond saw. Before testing, all specimens were annealed at 100 °C for 3 h to remove any possible residual stress introduced during the fabrication process.

3.2 Interlaminar fracture experiments

Fracture tests for both SENB and DCB specimens were performed at different temperatures, which are -80, -50, 20 and 50 °C, on an Instron 5567 machine with an environmental chamber. The loading rate was 1.0 mm/min for all tests. At least 4 samples were tested for each system. For SENB tests, K_{IC} can be determined from [11]:

$$K_{IC} = \frac{P}{B\sqrt{W}} f(a/W) \quad (1)$$

$$f(a/W) = f(\alpha) = 6\alpha^{1/2} \frac{[1.99 - \alpha(1 - \alpha)(2.15 - 3.93\alpha + 2.7\alpha^2)]}{(1 + 2\alpha)(1 - \alpha)^{3/2}} \quad (2)$$

where P is maximum load at crack initiation, W specimen width, B specimen thickness, a initial crack length and $f(\alpha)$ is non-dimensional shape factor. Then, G_{IC} is obtained from K_{IC} with given Young's modulus (E) and Poisson's ratio (ν):

$$G_{IC} = \frac{(1 - \nu^2)K_{IC}^2}{E} \quad (3)$$

Mode I DCB interlaminar fracture test was conducted based on ASTM Standard D5528 [12]. The load-displacement curve was recorded and crack growth monitored with a travelling microscope. The delamination fracture energy, G_{IC} , is obtained using the Modified Beam Theory (MBT) method:

$$G_{IC} = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + |\Delta|)} \quad (4)$$

where P is applied load, δ load-point displacement and $|\Delta|$ modification of measured crack length.

3.3 Results and discussion

Figure 3 shows the temperature effect on fracture toughness K_{IC} of neat epoxy (E) and 6 wt% nano-rubber modified epoxy (R6). From -80 °C to 50 °C, K_{IC} of un-modified epoxy is relatively stable with temperature. Nano-rubber modified epoxies always show higher K_{IC} than un-modified epoxies; but the toughening effect is more prominent at 20 °C and 50 °C.

Figure 4 shows the temperature effect on interlaminar fracture energy G_{IC} of unmodified laminates and nano-rubber modified laminates. In the inset, "E-matrix" indicates composite laminates with neat epoxy matrix; "R6-matrix" stands for composite laminates with modified epoxy matrix having 6 wt% nano-rubber. Here, G_{IC} of E-matrix laminates display a moderately increasing trend with temperature, especially at 50 °C due to a large elastic modulus reduction at high temperature [13]. By contrast, G_{IC} of R6-matrix laminates are more sensitive to temperature change increasing from -80 °C to 20 °C but decreasing notably at 50 °C.

To examine the toughness transfer from neat and nano-rubber modified epoxies to their composite laminates at different temperature, we can compare their G_{IC} values to those of the laminates. However, we need to know their temperature-dependent Young's moduli and use Eq. (3) to obtain G_{IC} . Thus, for neat epoxies, we took these values (no result at -80 °C) from Deng et al. [13]; and for the nano-rubber modified epoxies with 6 wt% particles (or 6.9 vol%), we assumed a constant value, 0.6 GPa, for nano-

rubber [6] and the values of Young's modulus of nano-rubber modified epoxy at different temperatures were approximately estimated [6], which may be underestimated at -50 °C.

Figure 3 Temperature effect on fracture toughness of neat (E) and modified R6 bulk epoxies.

Figure 4 Temperature effect on fracture energy of composite laminates with neat (E) and modified (R6) epoxy matrices.

Figure 5 compares the toughening efficiency of E and R6 and their composite laminates against mode I delamination in the temperature range -50 to 50 °C. G_{IC} of E-matrix laminates are much higher than the neat matrix (E) at all temperatures. This indicates effective matrix toughness transferability plus significant contribution from crack-wake fibre bridging. For the R6-matrix laminates, at -50 °C, G_{IC} is higher than the rubber modified matrix (R6) and even higher than that of the E-matrix laminates, confirming full transferability of matrix toughness due to rubber toughening as well as fibre bridging. However, at 20 °C and 50 °C, G_{IC} of R6-matrix laminates are much lower than R6 alone. This finding reveals that rubber toughening is discouraged by the fibre constraint. It is likely that the nano-rubber particles weaken the fibre/matrix interface and reduce the fibre bridging effect to resist delamination in the laminates. Detailed study on the toughening mechanisms will be discussed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The toughening effects of nano-rubber particles in epoxy and in epoxy/carbon fibre composites were studied at a range of temperatures from -80 to 50 °C. The results obtained show that, at -80 to 20

°C, nano-rubber increases the fracture energy of bulk epoxy and the interlaminar toughness of epoxy/carbon fibre composite laminates. However, the toughening efficiency of the nano-rubber varies with temperature. Rubber toughening in bulk epoxy at -50°C is less significant compared to 20 and 50 °C. However, the interlaminar G_{IC} of the rubber modified fibre composite at this temperature benefits from the cooperative rubber toughening and fibre bridging effects. At higher temperature of 50 °C, the nano-rubber particles slightly increase the interlaminar G_{IC} of the composite laminates even though they increase G_{IC} of bulk epoxy remarkably.

Figure 5 Comparison of nano-rubber toughening efficiency.

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